

The Greek Plague and Peloponnesian War

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Words like “epidemic” and “pandemic” (and “panic”!) have become part of our daily discourse. These words are Greek in origin, and they point to the fact that the Greeks of antiquity thought a lot about disease, both in its purely medical sense, and as a metaphor for the broader conduct of human affairs. What the Greeks called the “plague” (*loimos*) features in some memorable passages in Greek literature.

One such description sits at the very beginning of western literature. Homer’s *Iliad*, (around 700BC), commences with a description of a plague that strikes the Greek army at Troy. Agamemnon, the leading prince of the Greek army, insults a local priest of Apollo called Chryses.

Apollo is the plague god – a destroyer and healer – and he punishes all the Greeks by sending a pestilence among them. Apollo is also the archer god, and he is shown firing arrows into the Greek army with a terrible effect:

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Apollo strode down along the pinnacles of Olympus angered in his heart, carrying on his shoulders the bow and the hooded quiver; and the shafts clashed on the shoulders of the god walking angrily. ...
 Terrible was the clash that rose from the bow of silver. First, he went after the mules and the circling hounds, then let go a tearing arrow against the men themselves and struck them. The corpse fires burned everywhere and did not stop burning.

In this background, we can understand the significance of the Greek plague of 5th century BCE and draw its contemporary relevance.

The Greek Plague

In the 2nd year of the Peloponnesian War, 430 BCE, an outbreak of plague erupted in Athens. The illness would persist throughout scattered parts of Greece and the eastern Mediterranean until finally dying out in 426 BCE. The origin of the epidemic occurred in sub-Saharan Africa just south of Ethiopia. The disease swept north and west through Egypt and Libya across the Mediterranean Sea into Persia and Greece. The plague entered Athens through the city's port of Piraeus. The famous Greek historian Thucydides recorded the outbreak in his monumental work on the Peloponnesian war (431-404 BCE) between Athens and Sparta. According to various scholars, by its end, the epidemic killed upwards of 1/3 of the population; a population which numbered 250,000-300,000 in the 5th century BCE. By most accounts, the plague which struck

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Athens was the most lethal episode of illness in the period of Classical Greece history.

Narratives of the Greek Plague

About 270 years after the *Iliad*, plague is the centrepiece of two great classical Athenian works – Sophocles' *Oedipus the King*, and Book 2 of Thucydides' *History of the Peloponnesian War*.

Thucydides (c.460-400BC) and Sophocles (490-406BC) would have known one another in Athens, although it is hard to say much more than that for lack of evidence. The two works mentioned above were produced at about the same time. The play *Oedipus* was probably written about 429 BC, and the plague of Athens took place in 430-426 BC.

Thucydides writes prose, not verse (as Homer and Sophocles do), and he worked in the comparatively new field of "history" (meaning "enquiry" or "research" in Greek). His focus was the Peloponnesian war fought between Athens and Sparta, and their respective allies, between 431 and 404 BC.

Thucydides' description of the plague that struck Athens in 430 BC is one of the great passages of Greek literature. One of the remarkable things about it is how focused it is on the general social response to the pestilence, both those who died from it and those who survived.

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Health Crisis

The description of the plague immediately follows on from Thucydides' renowned account of Pericles' Funeral Oration (it is significant to note that Pericles himself died of the plague in 429 BC, whereas Thucydides caught it but survived).

Thucydides gives a general account of the early stages of the plague – its likely origins in north Africa, its spread in the broader regions of Athens, the struggles of the doctors to deal with it, and the high mortality rate of the doctors themselves.

Nothing seemed to ameliorate the crisis – not medical knowledge or other forms of learning, nor prayers or oracles. Indeed, “in the end people were so overcome by their sufferings that they paid no further attention to such things”.

He describes the symptoms in some detail – the burning feeling of sufferers, stomach-aches and vomiting, the desire to be totally naked without any linen resting on the body itself, the insomnia and the restlessness.

The next stage, after seven or eight days, if people survived that long, saw the pestilence descend to the bowels and other parts of the body – genitals, fingers and toes. Some people even went blind.

Thucydides provided a vivid account of a variety of ailments which afflicted the diseases. “Violent heats in the head; redness and inflammation of the eyes; throat and tongue quickly suffused with blood; breath became unnatural and fetid; sneezing and hoarseness; violent cough’ vomiting; retching; violent convulsions; the body externally not so hot to the touch, nor yet pale; a livid color inkling to red; breaking out in pustules and ulcers.” (2.49-2.50)

Words indeed fail one when one tries to give a general picture of this disease; and as for the sufferings of individuals, they seemed almost beyond the capacity of human nature to endure. Those with strong constitutions survived no better than the weak.

Thucydides further described patients whose fever was so intense that they preferred to be naked than wear any clothing which

Thucydides also focuses on the breakdown in traditional values where self-indulgence replaced honour, where there existed no fear of god or man. As for offences against human law, no one expected to live long enough to be brought to trial and punished: instead, everyone felt that a far heavier sentence had been passed on him.

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touched their skin; some even preferred to be submerged in cold water. Thucydides observed that the ill were “tormented by an unceasing thirst” which was not satiated regardless of the amount of liquids consumed. Many of the sick found it difficult to sleep, instead, displaying a constant restlessness. Many of the sufferers died within 7-9 days from the onset of symptoms.

Moral Consequences of Plague

The most terrible thing was the despair into which people fell when they realized that they had caught the plague; for they would immediately adopt an attitude of utter hopelessness, and by giving in in this way, would lose their powers of resistance.

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Concluding Remarks

Thucydides offers us a narrative of a pestilence that is different in all kinds of ways from what we face. The full description of the plague in Book 2 lasts only for about five pages, although it seems so intense and enduring.

The first outbreak of the plague lasted two years, after which it struck a second time, although with less virulence. When Thucydides picks up very briefly the thread of the epidemic a little bit later (3.87) he provides numbers of the deceased: 4,400 hoplites (citizen-soldiers), 300 cavalrymen and an unknown number of ordinary people. Nothing did the Athenians so much harm as this, or so reduced their strength for war.

The lessons that we learn from the coronavirus crisis will come from our own experiences of it. Reading Thucydides can help us perceive how much the ancients suffered. Thucydides offers

us a painful description of a city-state in a crisis that is as poignant and powerful now, as it was in 430BC.

While trying to reduce the pain, we cannot afford to panic, in spite of the intensity of the pain. We are called to be patient, waiting and hopeful. In spite of... Plague and pestilence have been with us from time immemorial! Though painful and tragic, we shall still overcome!

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